

**MUNICIPAL FACILITIES PROVISION, ADEQUACY,
FUNCTIONALITY AND MANAGEMENT: A SINE-QUA-NON TO
VALUE RE-ORIENTATION OF UNDERGRADUATES IN
NIGERIAN HIGHER EDUCATION**

Olorunfemi, Praise Oluwayemisiⁱ

Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education, Obafemi Awolowo University,
Osun State, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

Abstract:

The essence of higher education is to ensure value re-orientation and social transformation in our lives for national culture that would entrench and reshape national character and image via effective student affairs administration. This is with a view to promoting national image, healthier, stronger and courageous graduates; respect for human life, corporate and national values. The study therefore examined student affairs administration in higher education as a tool for value re-orientation and social transformation of the undergraduates. The study adopted survey research design. Using a self-designed and pilot-tested questionnaire, data were collected from a random sample of 400 drawn from four universities in the southwestern geopolitical zone of the country. Using proportionate sampling technique, 21, 24, 48 and 307 respondents were drawn from Redeemer's University (RUN), Adeleke University (AU), Oduduwa University (OUI) and Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU) respectively. Data were analysed using simple percentage. The results showed that municipal facilities were adequately available (89%), functional (98%) and consistently managed (90%) in both RUN and AU. However, these facilities were in short supplies in OUI (42%) and OAU (48%). Thus, it was recommended that more concerns should be shown to the provision, adequacy and management of municipal facilities in the universities such that the potential values in those facilities are benefited to reshape the value system of students thereby enhancing their social transformational process.

ⁱ Correspondence: email abranoe@yahoo.com

Keywords: student affairs administration; higher education; value re-orientation; social transformation

1.1 Introduction

Value is importance, significance, worth or usefulness of an item that is genuine. Value is a construct man places on an item. In this discuss, value is attached to usefulness of university education in Nigeria. The positive development of any individual, group and society is a function of value outcomes. Education is a requirement for societal formation, societal change and transformation. It is a calculated action that has power to add value to the life of its seekers and those who possess it. Education that is of value is education that has worth, power, strong, useful, desired, quality, important and desirable for its own sake. It is education that combines both knowledge and skills, thereby making it education that is required for national development.

Functional education is that, that equips the learner with useful knowledge, skills, vocation and culture that the learner, after graduating, can put the knowledge, skills, vocation and culture into use when employed or for self-employment and or creating jobs for others. Functional education makes the graduates productive. Productivities of these graduates count toward economic development of the nation. Functional education in its true meaning is a worthy activity that prepares an individual for useful life now and here and for the future. It is a good commodity for an individual, community and the general society. It is a weapon that helps those who are faithful and wants to equip themselves with it for better now and the future. It is a weapon for fighting the power of ignorance. University graduates in Nigeria are expected to exhibit some results of the worthy education received.

A look at the curriculum of Nigeria's university education leaves no one in doubt that graduates of this level of education would be graduates with added values provided the contents of the curriculum are effectively taught and there is mastery of what is taught to the students (National Policy). Value re-orientation is a re-assessment, take a look again and put something back on course because it has gone off-course. Education has gone off-course in Nigeria and the values expected from it, lost. There is therefore the need to redeem education in Nigeria through value re-orientation in the system now. Re-orientation is to bring back the lost values in the university system of education in Nigeria. A periodic evaluation of Nigeria's university education system is needed to keep the system on track. It is a check to make sure that what values education should give to the learners at the university level is of worthy quality that meets the need of the learners and his society. The mere mention of value re-orientation

in Nigeria's university education is an acceptance that the value expected to be given out through university education to its students is not the reality on ground. Values that were known before are not the same being those experienced today. Today's values are now put to question, hence the need for a re-orientation of education and its values at this level. Re-orientation is to make education functional again, in terms of values, knowledge, skills, vocation and culture for national development.

1.2 Value-Based Education

Value based education is education with contents that are of worth to the learner. Education that equips the learner with values that become embedded in him/her for life. The values are indices for the learner and his nation's economic and other positive developments. Value re-orientation in Nigeria's university education is an affirmation that the value education was known for in the past at this level has eroded down. The re-orientation is a strategy and means of returning to value based education. Three major components of value-based education are inputs into education, expected outcomes and ultimate outcomes. Lecturers and school management are to make value-based inputs into the system. The values should be those that would bring development and advancement of the students and the society. There are expected outcomes from a student who has gone through education that is value based. Patriotism, loyalty, politeness, kindness, tolerance, acceptance, courage, friendliness, trustworthy and dependability according to Ikonne (2012) are some of the expected outcomes. The ultimate outcomes, Ikonne (2012) stated, may include competence, diligence, discipline, orderliness, integrity, selflessness, cooperation and unity. Interest in development, growth and advancement are functions of functional education. Furthermore, value-based education is expected to produce men and women that value what their society holds as values. Different people hold different values in a particular behaviour or thing, but the society expects value-based education to make the learners functional and or productive and uphold the society's values. The nation in turn expects its educational system to turn out products that are knowledgeable, skillful and can contribute to national growth. Value is the worth education offers to its learners. Value is the importance education gives to individuals, communities and societies. The importance is observed and measured in terms of economic growth, health improvement, employability and employment opportunities to graduates of the educational system, advancement of university graduates to further studies in universities and other tertiary institutions and the general improvement in all aspects of life of the individuals, communities and larger societies. Value-based education is true education. White (2000) stated that: *"True education means more than pursuing a certain*

course of study. It has to do with the whole person and with the whole period of existence possible to human beings. It is the harmonious development of the physical, mental, and spiritual powers”.

The success of any organization, whether private or public, depends largely on the ability for it to acquire and maintain the human and physical resources for its existence. In the university system anywhere, the strongest element or ingredient that initiates sustains and promotes its existence and productivity is the student body. Based on this reasoning, the university must come to grip with the proper acquisition and proper administration of all affairs related to students. That is to say, giving the students the necessary love, care, guidance and protection, so as to sustain them. This has to be, if the university is to promote its own final goals and objectives of proper teaching, learning and research as well as to produce happier, healthier, well groomed and adjusted graduates.

Starting from 1973, there has been student population explosion and the universities were not adequate for the youth that want to further their education and that led to student unrest which led to the establishment of private universities for individuals who can afford it to cater for their educational needs. According to Imoke (2005) and Nigeria University Commission (NUC 2005), there is an ongoing reform which is geared towards expanding access, promoting and ensuring quality and increasing institutional efficiency and thereby be responsive and relevant towards the production of qualitative, globally competitive entrepreneurial and self-reliant graduate. Basically, the presence of learners is crucial to the existence of all the components of the university. Substantially, the presence of the students in the university is to acquire value-oriented knowledge that will lead to social transformation. It has also been noted that learning is a continuous process. This process can only be meaningful and successful with healthy and determined minds of both the learners, lecturers and all that combine to energize the institution known as the university (Adesina, 1981).

In those days, feeding was free and each student had a whole room to himself or herself, laundry services and all cleaning materials were served free. They queued for services and they do not do thing in a disorderly manner. However as the population increased gradually over the years, the University’s capacity to continue providing the basic welfare services such as feeding, decent accommodation and basic municipal facilities which could enhance learning became a problem as these were impinging on the universities’ level of funding. In Kwanashe’s view (1999), universities in Nigeria in general have been frustrated by various constraints *“ranging from crisis of students’ population, crisis of funding, crisis of relevance, disruption of students’ and staff unions to crisis*

of confidence". And due to inadequate fund and poor planning there was a total breakdown in the provision and management of basic facilities and amenities, particularly municipal facilities for students' welfare services and also a down turn in the educational value system.

It is on the basis of this prevailing predicament that the study sought to study municipal facilities provision, adequacy, functionality and management: a sine-qua-non to value re-orientation of undergraduates in Nigerian higher education.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

One of the ways of imbibing values that will lead to social transformation of university students is by providing adequate, functional and proper management of municipal facilities. Private and public universities have in recent times, experienced a down turn in values being instilled into students as a result of accommodation issues, transportation problems, conflict with management policies, inadequate supply of municipal facilities, in spite of the enormous resources expended on student affairs administration in private and public universities and of which resources are allocated to those student services and programmes that enhance student learning and success in relation to need and demand. This variation is alleged to be as a result of factors yet to be investigated; there is therefore a need to validate such allegation empirically.

It is generally accepted that students' municipal services are indispensable for the efficient management of any university in the world. Towards realizing these objectives, the government and university management must uphold the need to seriously provide all the necessary welfare services to students at all times.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

1. Examine the functionality, adequacy and management of inputs (personnel and materials) used in the student affairs unit in private and public universities.
2. Investigate the value oriented outputs (number of graduates per session, number of student crises per session, frequency of hitch-free supply of municipal facilities) of the division of student affairs in the study area;
3. Examine the value systems of private and public universities in the study area; and
4. Identify the challenges confronting the social transformation process of students' affairs' administration in the study area.

1.4 Research Question

To guide this study, the following research questions were raised.

1. How functional, adequate and management of inputs used in the division of student affairs in private and public universities in Osun State?
2. What are the value oriented outputs of the Division of Student Affairs in the selected universities?
3. What is the value system in private and public universities in the study area?
4. What are the challenges confronting the value re-orientation process of students' affairs' administration in the study area?

2. Roles of Student Affairs

An effective Department of students' affairs should exist in any university. It is this department, that usually articulates and translates students' complaints and aspirations, in a manner that would facilitate responsive and cost efficient decisions by the university authority, rather than just ignoring them. As the Division is the custodian of the total welfare of the students, it demands a careful selection for the appointment of competent, dedicated, selfless and suitable persons as the Dean of Students by the university authority. The Dean should be a father or mother who listens to students and accommodates their differences.

The Dean is responsible to the Top Executive (who is the Chairman of Students' Welfare Management Board) on matters affecting the Division, particularly students' matters. It is his responsibility to assign or delegate duties to able officers in the Division. Such important officers are the accommodation officer, the career officer, the counsellor, the finance officer, the sports staff, hall supervisors, store officers, maintenance officers and cleaners. He should also see that the right Private Caterers are recruited. The Dean has to control, coordinate and supervise the procurement and provision of adequate and quality equipment and cleaning materials in the sports section, students' halls of residence, counselling centre and student union secretariat as may be prescribed by the Students' Welfare Board. He also has to coordinate incentives like government and private scholarships, bursary schemes, medical emergency referral voucher, student union matters, general sanitation and maintenance of the halls. The successful management of the human and material resources in the Division therefore contributes immensely to the effective and efficient welfare services of the student.

2.1 Student Affairs and Provision of Municipal Facilities

According to Adesina (1981), student's welfare services are "*services concerned with needs and interest of the students' populace*". To him, of all services rendered to groups in the school or university system, that of the students should be a priority. This is so, because

a university is set up for students and not primarily for subsequent groups. Hence, without students, a university will never exist. Jacob,(1768) in the New Encyclopedia Britanica also sees students' welfare services as "services provided to students particularly disadvantaged, distressed and invulnerable persons or group". Ventareswarlu in Oni (1999), views that students' welfare services include not only 'growth' of facilities but also security, sustainability, equity, prudence and justice in its provision". According to Lawal (1999), students' welfare services comprise health matters, accommodation, feeding, sports and recreation. However, for the purpose of this study, students' welfare services or municipal facilities can be defined as the basic needs provided to students by the university for ensuring survival, comfort and conducive atmosphere for academic concentration and better performance. These services include among others student orientation, good feeding, decent accommodation, sports and recreational facilities, guidance and counselling, health and other social amenities, sound academic activities that is teaching and learning facilities and conducive environment.

The university has the mandate to give students all the necessary attention, care and services they deserve within the scope of the university, so that the students' aims and objectives of being in the university system are achieved. When there is adequate municipal facilities there will be orderliness, stealing will reduce, morals will be instilled and students will appreciate values that will to social transformation individually and the society at large. Towards this reasoning, the Nigerian Government like any other government has the greatest concern over the welfare and development of their youths in the universities. This has been implied in the National Policy on Education, (2004): page 7 Section 1, Paragraph 3 which says "...the quality of instruction at all levels has to be oriented towards inculcating: Respect for the worth and dignity of the individuals; Faith in man's ability to make rational decisions; Promotion of the Health of all children"

The Nigerian Constitution (1999) has summed up this strong philosophy of Education since it has taken the pains to express protection of student's interest. It sees students as having the equal rights based on social order when it says:

"The security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of the Government, and Paragraph 16, 2 (d) that suitable and adequate shelter, suitable and adequate food and welfare are provided for all citizens and Paragraph 17, 2(a) "In Furtherance of the social order – as every citizen shall have equality of rights obligations and opportunity before the law."

Paragraph 14, 2 (b)

Similarly, section S5.5(2) (h) University of Ibadan Act 1962 as amended, holds that *“the supervision of the welfare of students at the university and the regulation of their conduct is vested in the senate”* (Ojo 1995). In the opening speech of the Principal of the North East College of Arts and Science in 1974, which metamorphosed to University of Maiduguri the following year, emphasis was seriously laid on students’ welfare as he rightly said: *“for students to be properly educated morally and culturally oriented, committed to their studies, devoid of rioting and rebellious behaviour, they must be provided with maximum welfare facilities for extracurricular activities, sporting, games, athletics, accommodation, medical services and conducive environment for academic activities”*.

Against this backdrop, the university administration placed high premium on Division of Students’ Affairs. There was a strong conviction that students’ welfare was paramount. Moreso, decree No. 83 (1971) establishing the university conferred power on the administration to provide for students’ discipline and welfare. It specifically enjoins the Senate to be *“responsible for provision, control, supervision and formulation of Students’ Affairs policies”*. Professor A.S. Mikailu in a welcome address to fresh students in the 1998/99 session assured all students about the universities’ concern on their welfare. He said, *“we would do everything within our resources to improve your welfare so that your period of stay in the university will be a fruitful one”*. It is very clear that these excerpts alone, stress the concern and regards by the management and the government for the universal principles underlying the complete welfare of students, particularly the philosophy underlying the principles of health, dignity and worth of children which cannot be achieved without the provision of adequate basic welfare facilities. The realization of this philosophy for a meaningful education therefore relies to a large extent upon the ability of the university to provide and effectively manage whatever human and material resources at its disposal tagged for students’ welfare. In the reasoning of Ifadi (1988) the neglect of the responsibility of the welfare of the young, particularly, students *“culminates into moral decadence, chaos, and unrest in the university”*.

In the University system, some of the most crucial and relevant municipal services students cannot do without can be classified into four and their impact on students’ behaviour can be discussed at length. These are:

A. Social Services

These are students’ feeding, hostel accommodation, guidance and counseling, sports and recreation, security, transportation, religious, clubs and societies, banking and shopping services, adequate electricity and water supply.

B. Students’ feeding

Feeding can be defined as the supply of nourishing food or meal progressively and adequately to a person or group of persons, which, in the context of this study are the

students of the universities in Osun State. Although Nigerian Government as opined by Oladapo (1987), knew very well that even countries much richer and developed than it, *"wisely regarded feeding and accommodation as not integral part of their university education and avoided them"*. Nigeria at National level took the risk by giving it top priority consideration without foreseeing their future burdensomeness. Right from the inception of the Federal university in this state, the provision of students' feeding was considered a mandatory responsibility of the Obafemi Awolowo University. As the population then was manageable, the university could conveniently afford a whole catering unit vested in the Student Affairs Division. The main objective of this unit was to provide adequate and reasonable food both in quantity and quality at a very subsidized cost.

In Obafemi Awolowo University, students are encouraged to cook their meals and anyone who cannot cook can easily buy food in any of the eateries, restaurants and mama put around that are affordable. While Oduduwa University allows some of his students to live off campus, some are living on campus and those living on campus are not allowed to cook in the school hostel. In Redeemer's University, students are not allowed to cook but there are cafeterias where students buy food to eat at affordable prices. The constraint of not cooking in Redeemer's university is one of the factors causing agitations among the students. Adeleke University provides food for the student because it is part of the school fees although the school is subsidizing the meals.

C. Accommodation

The concept of accommodation in the university system can be both classroom and hostel which are very crucial to the meaningful and well-being of students on campus. In Maslow's view, (1954) shelter like food is a basic human requirement on earth. For a student, it is one thing to secure provisional admission into the university, it is quite another to get decent accommodation. Admission without accommodation to them is thus incomplete.

In Redeemer's University, they have excess hostel accommodation for students and they are still building more at the permanent site. Oduduwa University has some of its students living off campus while Adeleke University has enough accommodation for its students and even excess accommodation.

D. Guidance and Counseling

Guidance and counseling has been defined in many ways by various authors. Okon, (1984) defines guidance as a total programme of *"highly specialized activities implemented by all staff members to help individuals make wise and intelligent choices and decisions"*. Durojaiye (1972) views guidance and counseling in the context of total educational process as a *"complex process which encompasses the total needs of the individual student to be directed or guided"*. The guide is available to the individual in terms of educational,

social, emotional, health, vocational and leisure time needs and for the individual's preparation for a suitable occupation. That is the assistance may be educational, vocational, social, personal, emotional or moral and recreational aimed at helping individual to behave rationally and change his/her behavior positively by solving their problems and full development through interaction with the counselor who provides information. The inclusion of guidance and counselling as a programme in a school system is paramount as it will make students feel that they can be appropriately assisted by the administrators, lecturers, teachers, trained counsellors and other service staff interacting directly or indirectly with students for enhancing their welfare, social transformation and also a programme that will build the value system of the society.

E. Sports and Recreation

While sports refer to a game or activity involving physical exercise especially outdoors, in the fields, lanes, sky, mountains or water, recreation is a pleasurable occupation or amusement as Bulter in Lawal (1999) defines it as *"an activity that is not consciously performed for the sake of any reward beyond itself, which one usually engages in during leisure and which offers man an outlet for physical, mental, creative powers and in which he engages his inner desire and not because of outer compulsion"*. Sports and Recreation have been as old as man's creation. Many History books revealed to us that the early man on earth was a sportsman as he chased wild life and gathered leaves and berries for livelihood. The Roman's and Spartans were great sportsmen, Kingfisher (1999). Apart from the role played in body building and physical fitness sports and recreation excite the mind. In line with this logic it is often said and believed that *"An idle mind is the devil's workshop"* or *"All work and no play makes Jack a dull boy"*. These expressions preach and signify that neither inactivity nor excessive pressures, strains, stresses from the modern academic demand promotes positive wellbeing of the body and mind. Rather the individual becomes physically unfit or lured into emotional instability and all sorts of fraudulent behavior.

In the effort to neutralize these negative traits and break the monotonous and boring conditions of academic work and the difficult life of students arising from lack of good feeding, accommodation as well as the strangeness of the new environment, all universities should establish and maintain a virile programme on sporting and recreational activities under the supervision of full-time coaches. The sports offices of the universities are mostly located in the Students Affairs Division and the Sports Office in each university is headed by the Director of Sports and many coaches whose duties are:

- a) To be responsible for the arrangement of students participation in all sporting activities taking place internally, locally, nationally and internationally.

- b) To advise the University Management on all aspects of sporting activities including the procurement and provision of sports equipment and facilities. There is also a sports Committees in all universities appointed by the Vice-Chancellors whose duties are to coordinate the sporting activities on the Campus and beyond.

In the recent years, there has been the belief that television and satellite viewing services have replaced most of the indoor games and have reduced the attendance of cinema. Unfortunately, this has at the same time led to the decline of academic work performance in most universities as the students have found themselves spending more time before the television sets in common rooms, in their rooms or in the student centers than before their teachers and books. During leisure times students are supposed to visit parks, gardens, lawns and dam areas where one exists for recreational relaxations.

F. Transportation services

Transportation in the context of this study means all the necessary ways and means, used to enable the students move from one place to another in the course of the pursuit of their studies. Most of the universities operate on two or more campus or a large campus where boarding areas are far from academic and other service buildings and students have fear of covering considerable distance to the academic areas Nigerian Universities in general do not have sole responsibility of providing students' transportation for movement within the campus and beyond. It is necessary that transportation arrangements are facilitated by the university to bring in private transport associations like the Okadas, Bus or Taxi service schemes/associations to operate on campuses with maximum control. The absence of such arrangement can likely cause unnecessary suffering to students.

When Redeemer's university was in Redemption Camp, school bus usually moves on scheduled time to carry students from hostel to school area and vice versa and students are not allowed to use car while on campus. Students are also encouraged to queue up for buses. In Obafemi Awolowo University, we have buses and Okadas whose riders have the school Okada jacket on when working. In Oduduwa University there is the use of Okada and Keke Marua to transport student from one place to another within the Campus.

G. Academic Services

These are classrooms and lecture halls accommodation, library facilities, laboratory equipment, teaching and learning equipment, information and communication technology such as websites, computers, internet cafes, telephones, handsets,

bookshops, printing press, field and practical trips and work and students adviser advisee services.

H. Classroom (lecture halls) laboratories and technological workshops

In Ojo (1995) view, the universities anywhere are supposed to have adequate classrooms, facilities, science laboratories, lecture halls. *“Proper academic environment has far-reaching effects on the learning process”*. As its absence, he says *“leads to the gradual decay of the symbolic things that help to pattern students’ behaviour”*. Students should have access to well ventilated classrooms or lecture halls, large enough to accommodate large number of students for large lectures. Science laboratories are supposed to be well equipped with science equipment for practical. Due to the poorly old fashioned equipment nature of the science and medical laboratories in the Universities, most people take the Nigerian Science graduates as ‘half-baked products’ compared to graduates from oversea universities. As elaborated by Okebukola (2002).

Lack of access to current literature and replacement of obsolete equipment in the university laboratories *“account for the rise of out-dated methodology in the conduct of research”*. Many researchers he disclosed *“are knowledgeable and skilled in only what they picked up during doctoral training in sophisticated laboratories overseas”*. To worsen the well-functioning and performance of the laboratories and workshops in most universities in Nigeria in general, the Nigerian Electric Power Authority (NEPA) supply is disappointingly unreliable and mean. They have even killed the zeal of the Nigerian Industry at large.

I. Students Medical/Health Services

These include health and sanitation, clinics and medical centers, hospitals, treatment of diseases, inoculations and vaccination against diseases HIV Aids treatment, curative and preventive supplements or drugs and campaigns on various health problems. Next in the series of important students’ welfare services which should be provided in the University system is Medical and Health services. Health is often said to be *“next to godliness”*. It is a fundamental right of every individual, nation, community, people irrespective of religion, creed, sex, values and beliefs. In a community like the university system where there are clusters of students and staff there has to be effective and well-coordinated team of Medical personnel entrusted with the responsibility of diagnosing, management, maintaining, preventing and curing the ever changing trend in disease technology. The researcher noticed that on most campuses of the Universities in Nigeria, there is health centers referred to as Sickbays, University Clinics, Medical and Health Services Unit or Department, Hospitals as the case may be.

2.2 Value System in Private and Public Universities

Both private and public universities have values, norms, rules and regulation that are acceptable to the university communities. The private institutions are more rigid with their rules and regulations unlike the public universities. There is high moral standard in the private universities that will lead to the transformation of the society.

Magaji (2014) made it clear that core values are central in this discourse and they form the major, basic or main variables that make education valuable and functionally useful to man. The graduates produced now are limited in knowledge and skills. They cannot defend their certificates in writing or verbally. He defined value as the worth or importance, education is expected to teach and offer its students. Education is meant to give values that prepare its graduates to be functional, leading to economic growth, healthy society, employment chances, access to higher education and skills development, education for the whole person and for life, and education that will solve problems. People, who are truthful and honest citizens, are seen and counted as those who know what value is. Such people are good examples to the younger one. Model citizens won't sell their consciences for nothing less than value. These are some of the values in Nigeria's education that are lost. The absence of these values is what went wrong with the system of education under consideration in this paper. Many university graduates now cannot demonstrate in practical terms what education has given them after a minimum of eighteen (18) years stay in primary, secondary schools and university. Most of these graduates of the system cannot be employed or even think of self-employment and add values to their lives and contribute to nation's economic developments. There is therefore a need to bring back values into the education system in order to make education functional.

Core values are seen in well- educated individuals who are able to effectively participate in the political, social and economic institutions that are the foundation of a democratic society.

Educational core values should be able to:

1. Mold the behaviours of the youths to meet societal standards.
2. Shape the future of individuals and society.
3. Expose students to diversities and different points of views of other people.
4. Have positive influence of peers on students conduct and achievement.
5. Provide variety of experiences through parents and community engagement in the schools, such as Family Forum in Redeemer's university and Parents Consultative Forum (PC) as in Babcock University, where parents and school administrator meet to share their valuable experiences and agree on which

values be passed to the students for positive development of which is missing in public universities.

6. Give individual benefits that include acquisition of academic knowledge and skills.
7. Introduce collective welfare of societies, institutions and freedoms to succeed and continue into the future.
8. Equip graduates with knowledge and different skills that they would apply into diverse endeavours with the aim of developing themselves and the nation.

Ethical, moral and natural goods are among core values education should teach learners. Moral goods are values that have to do with the conduct of persons, usually leading to praise or blame. Kant (1724-1804) thought of moral value as a unique and universally identifiable property. A moral good is anything which one is obligated to strive towards. Natural goods in the other hand have to do with objects and not praises. Ethics lean itself on moral rather than natural goods. Different people have different values on particular behaviour or thing. In everything and every conduct of an individual, value should be introduced for a worthy society (Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia).

2.3 Challenges Confronting the Value Re-Orientation Process of Students' Affairs' Administration

A. Challenges of Student Welfare and Provision of Municipal Facilities

As for accommodation, hostel and lecture halls were inadequate so much so that equipment and facilities are heavily overstretched. Consequently, without alternative measures, students will resort to hardship which will eventually frustrate their hopes and expectation of improved environment for learning. This situation could culminate to series of serious problems and crisis ranging from despondency, stress, conflicts, violence, destructions, vandalism, malpractices, thefts, armed robbery, cultism and related crimes. This state of hopelessness usually precipitates serious problems of students' unrest in any institution which in turn affects the value system and effective administration of Division of Student Affairs in carrying out their duties.

A study conducted at Michigan State University by Beit-Hallahmi in Bello (1983) revealed that out of 91 percent of students interviewed, asked for university to provide facilities to reduce psychological problems faced by the students. It is strongly believed that the greatest problem of students was that of feeding and other municipal facilities. The frustrations arising from the inadequate provision of municipal facilities coupled with the mismanagement of whatever little that was given added to the psychological, emotional and physiological stress which certainly had adverse effect on their academic

standard and educational development of the universities in particular and the country in general.

B. Health problems

Bello (1983) also conducted a study on the problem of Health of Students in University of Lagos and he identified some prominent problems plaguing the student's studies which ranged from poor feeding, emotional, social instability, lack of proper accommodation and unhealthy living environment.

According to the researcher, the problem of accommodation is high in Obafemi Awolowo University, the buildings are not adequate and the toilet facilities are not well maintained. We have dilapidated buildings and leaking roofs. It was God that saved some ladies at Moremi hall as at 2015 when one of the rooms gutted fire. Health talks can also be used to restore values into the lives of students.

C. Funding

For the survival, management, execution and maintenance of any project in any organization, availability of funds is the single most important resource. It is quite often said that *"Get funding right and most other things will fall in place"* Okebukola (2002). A major source of the Federal and State Government university system in Nigeria in general is the Government. Funds are allocated as capital and recurrent grants. Unfortunately, allocations made are more of theory on paper than what actually gets to the universities. And most universities do not generate their own resources, the story is always 'no funds', universities are starved, *"they are collapsing,"* etc. However, from most indications, there is a general consensus by many writers that the unending controversial under-funding of the universities which has persisted without an improvement has been the greatest impediment for perfecting the management and governance in the university system, particularly, in the universities under study. Hence the commitment of the government in general and the university in particular to the provision and management of the student affairs is heavily dependable on the availability and provision of adequate funding by the government to the universities and/or the ability of the university to generate revenue to supplement government's subvention. Feeding could not continue, additional accommodation structures could not be feasible and even supply of teaching facilities became stagnant. Consenting on the collapsing condition of university funding, Kwanashie, (1999) further observed that the crisis of funding is one of the major crisis the universities have been facing. Similarly, Dogo (1981) opined that the predicament of Division of Students' Affairs in the university boils down to inadequacy of funds on one hand and the problem of efficient administration on the other hand. In Redeemer's university, low student in

take contributes to low fund generated by the school and same goes to other private universities in Osun State.

D. Overdependence on other units

The Division of Students' Affairs works with other units within the university. Division of Student Affairs, when there is electricity problem in the hostel, beckons on the electrical department to fix the problem, the same goes for supply of water to the hostels and other units. When there is delay on the side of those units to respond to emergency situation, the students and everyone blames it on the Division of Student Affairs.

E. Inadequate personnel

The personnel working with the Division of Student Affairs in Redeemer's University is total of 21, serving 1500 students. While in Obafemi Awolowo University, we have 74 Division of Student Affairs personnel serving over 37000 students. From the two universities we can see that the personnel are inadequate to serve the whole community. In Adeleke University, they have 30 personnel working in their Division of Student Affairs.

F. Too many problems

The Division of Student Affairs is continually faced with too many problems on a daily basis. Psychological problems of students from home, problems with student mobilization for NYSC, too frequent emergency situations.

E. Vandalisation of properties

The continuous vandalisation of school properties by students during their protest always destroy facilities that are repaired with money that are meant to construct new ones in the school.

3. Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey design. The present study assessed the municipal facilities provision, adequacy, functionality and management: a sine-qua-non to value re-orientation of undergraduates in Nigerian higher education. The resources utilized, that is inputs (personnel and materials) to Division of Students Affairs and their outputs (number of graduates per session, number of student crises per session, frequency of hitch-free supply of municipal facilities). The value systems, means of re-orienting the university value system and how it can lead to social transformation. The study population comprised of all the six private and two public universities students, Heads of Department, and staff members of the division of student affairs in Osun State. The sample study comprises 400 students, 15 HODs, four Deans of student affairs

(or their proxies) and four student affairs officers or secretaries. The sample population is 28, 870 students (Obafemi Awolowo University: 22,170, Adeleke University: 1700, Redeemers' University, 1500 and Oduduwa University 3500). Multistage sampling procedure was adopted for the study. Four hundred students, 15 HODs and four sampling procedure was adopted for the study. From the six private universities and the two public universities, proportionate sampling technique was used to select one public university and three private universities. From the selected public university, five faculties was selected using simple random sampling technique, while three faculties selected from each of the private universities using proportionate sampling technique. From each of the faculties, five departments were selected using simple random sampling technique. From the departments so selected, 10 students comprising off campus and on campus will be selected in the ratio of 2:3 (to involve both residential and non-residential students) using purposive sampling technique. Ten students was also selected from each of the 15 departments in the three private universities using simple random sampling technique. Research instruments are the tools the researcher used to collect data and these include Questionnaires. They were used to obtain information on a number of issues and also assess the situation on ground. The questionnaires was also used to obtain data on the feelings and perception of the students and Heads of Departments, Deans of student affairs, students affairs officers or secretaries on the existing value systems, adequacy, functionality and management of municipal facilities as a tool for social transformation., and their perceptions of the problems associated with the situation on ground from 2012 to 2016. Fixed and non-fixed response types of questionnaires were used. These are Inputs, Outputs Questionnaire (IOQ), and Students' Assessment of Universities Performance Questionnaire (SAUPQ). The IOQ was administered on the Deans (or their proxies) of Student Affairs to identify resources and output of the Student Affairs Units; the SAUPQ was administered on students (on campus and off campus mode) to evaluate the extent of the university performance as regards students matters; Questionnaires were used to collect data for the research. The questionnaires were distributed personally by the researcher to ensure high percentage return of the research instrument. The administration of questionnaire was carried out at alternate or separate days and time. After all data was collected, the data was coded and entered in the computer for analysis using the statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.

The researcher used descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentage to answer the research questions. The data collected were analyzed using appropriate descriptive statistics such as bar charts, pie charts, percentage and frequency tables. The inputs were weighed against the outputs of the Division of

Student Affairs in the study areas. The Likert scale used in the questionnaire having strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree were compressed to agree and disagree to form two opinion sides and presented using the above statistical tools.

4. Results and Discussion of Findings

The results showed that municipal facilities were adequately available (89%), functional (98%) and consistently managed (90%) in both RUN and AU. However, these facilities were in short supplies in OUI (42%) and OAU (48%).

Research Question 1: How functional, adequate and management of inputs used in the division of student affairs in private and public universities in Osun State?

Table 1: The functionality, adequacy and proper management of Municipal facilities (inputs) in the study areas

S/N	Items	Adequately available	Functionality	Consistently managed
01	Obafemi Awolowo University	(143 respondents agreed) 48%	(143 respondents agreed) 48%	(143 respondents agreed) 48%
02	Redeemer's University	(19 respondents agreed) 89%	(20 respondents agreed) 98%	(19 respondents agreed) 90%
03	Adeleke University	(21 respondents agreed) 89%	(23 respondents) 98%	(21 respondents) 90%
04	Oduduwa University	(20 respondents agreed) 42%	(20 respondents agreed) 42%	(20 respondents agreed) 42%

Research Question 2: What are the socially transformed outputs of the Division of Student Affairs in the Selected Universities?

Output Tables

Table 2: Value Oriented Outputs of the Division of Student Affairs in Obafemi Awolowo University

Items	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Total number of graduates	-----	9713	5728	4714	Awaiting
Total number of students mobilized for NYSC	-----	9713	5728	4714	Awaiting
Number of student crises on campus					Nil

Source: Field work 2017

Table 3: Socially Transformed and Value Oriented Outputs of the Division of Student Affairs in Redeemer’s University

Items	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Total number of graduates	439	483	563	587	613
Total number of students mobilized for NYSC	439	483	563	587	613
Number of student crises on campus	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

Source: Fieldwork 2017

Table 4: Socially Transformed and Value Oriented Outputs of the Division of Student Affairs in Oduduwa University

Items	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Total number of graduates	Nil	109	290	300	350
Total number of students mobilized for NYSC	Nil	109	290	300	350
Number of student crises on campus	Nil	Nil	Nil	1	1

Source: Fieldwork 2017

Table 5: Socially Transformed and Value Oriented Outputs of the Division of Student Affairs in Output table for Adeleke University

Items	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Total number of graduates	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	266
Total number of students mobilized for NYSC	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	266
Number of student crises on campus	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

Source: Fieldwork 2017

Research Question 3: What is the value system in private and public universities in the study area?

Table 6: Value Judgement or Ranking in Selected Universities in Study Areas

S/N	Value System	OAU	RUN	AU	OUI
01	HIGH	(80 respondents agreed) 27%	(19 respondents agreed) 89%	(23 respondents agreed) 95%	(31 respondents agreed) 65%
02	LOW	(217 respondents disagreed) 73%	(2 respondents disagreed) 11%	(1 respondent disagreed) 5%	(17 respondents disagreed) 35%

Source: Fieldwork 2017.

The table showed that, 80 respondents (27%) in Obafemi Awolowo University agreed that the value system is high while 217 respondents (73%) disagreed, that the value system is low. In Redeemer’s University, (19 respondents agreed) 89% agreed that the value system is high. While (2 respondents disagreed) 11% disagreed, that the value system is low. In Adeleke University (23 respondents agreed) 95% agreed that the value

system is high. While (1 respondent disagreed) 5% disagreed, that the value system is low. In Oduduwa University (31 respondents agreed) 65% agreed that the value system is high. While (17 respondents disagreed) 35% disagreed, that the value system is low.

Research Question 4: What are the challenges confronting students' affairs' administration in the study area?

From the instrument administered to the Deans of Students Affairs, the challenges confronting their administrations are as follows and they vary from one university although there are similar challenges.

A. Obafemi Awolowo University

Lack of funds and supporting facilities for the Division of Student Affairs. The division needs all the help it can get from the school administration to be able to handle the herculean task of managing the affairs of students. Also the dam needs to be restructured and more boreholes to be dug. There is no proper data base, inadequate hostels poor internet network for online duties

B. Oduduwa University

The division is having the challenges of space, inadequate materials, inadequate personnel and over dependency on other units to respond to urgent situations.

C. Redeemer's University

The division is having the challenges of inadequate staff, low student population leading to inadequate funding and over dependency on other units to respond to urgent situations.

D. Adeleke University

In Adeleke University, the researcher got to know from the instrument that there is no problem for now and they are not facing any challenges, because, the proprietor has made adequate provision for everything needed.

4.1 Summary

The study examined the adequacy, functionality and management of inputs in terms of materials and personnel used by the Division of Student of Affairs Administration, the outputs in terms of hitch free supply of municipal facilities, number of student unrest and graduation rates. The value systems in the school and the challenges encountered.

5. Conclusion

The study concluded that municipal facilities were adequately available (89%), functional (98%) and consistently managed (90%) in both RUN and AU. However, these facilities were in short supplies in OUI (42%) and OAU (48%) and that the provision of

adequate, functional and proper management of municipal facilities to student is second to none in value orientation and social transformation of students and society at large.

6. Recommendations

University authority in collaboration with the government should endeavour to build more hostels for students in order to avoid the problem of inadequacy of hostel buildings and overcrowding. Also, hostels should be located close to the lecture rooms for easy accessibility by students; also dilapidated buildings should be renovated. A conducive accommodation will promote value re-orientation and lead to social transformation.

Students also have the responsibility of keeping the hostels clean. They would achieve this by cleaning their rooms, toilets and bathrooms, sweeping their corridors and also dumping refuse where appropriate. One of the values that ought to be instilled into Nigerian graduates is the maintenance culture.

The school management should provide adequate fund for the Division of Student Affairs and the division needs all the help it can get from the school administration to be able to handle the herculean task of managing the affairs of students.

Students affairs is the key unit in instilling values to students, all other units within the university should support to give the students the best for the society to have value-oriented and socially transformed graduates.

References

1. Africa South of Sahara: Society for International Development, Page 999, Isola
2. Bello University, M.Sc. Thesis, Faculty of Administration, ABU, Zaria.
3. Bello, J. Y. (1983). *The Identification of Problems Facing Students of Advanced Teachers Colleges in Nigeria.* Ph.D Thesis, Faculty of Education, ABU, Zaria. pp. 38.
4. Ikonne, C. N. (2012). *Value- Based Education.* Paper presented at the First North West Nigeria Union Mission of Seventh-day Adventist Church Teachers Retreat in Benin City, Nigeria. August 31– September 5, 2012.
5. Kwanashie, M. (1987). *"Expansion verses consolidation in the University System"*

6. Lawal B. I. (1999). Crisis Management in an organization: A case study of Ahmadu
7. Lawal, L. (1978). "Hands Off: Versities advised on students feeding:" A.B.U.
8. Okebukola, P. (2000). The State of University Education in Nigeria, NUC Abuja,
9. Okebukola, P.; Ibrahim, A.; Bola, B.; and Ayo, B. (2003). Private sector participation in University hostel development and management. NUC Abuja 2003, Abuja. Ola & Sons, Sabon Gari Zaria.
10. Oladapo, I. O. (1987). Financial and Administrative Management of State
11. Oladipo, O. (1996). 'Students welfare issues and prospects. Student union, ABU, 1996.
12. Oladipupo, K. J. (1981). Recommendations on 1981 student's unrest in ABU, Zaria.
13. Olakanmi & Co (2008). The Nigerian Constitutions, 1963, 1979, 1999. A Compendium (3rd.ed). (Promulgation, 1999 No. 24, section 18 (1), (2) and (3) (a),(b)&(c), Abuja, Law Lords Publications.
14. Oni, S.B. (1999 ed). Policies and Strategies for Sustainable Development In p. 1 (front page).
15. Magaji, S. (2014) Value Re-Orientation in Secondary School Education in Nigeria. Knowledge Review Volume 29 No. 1, April, 2014.
16. Students say 'No' to lectures. Nigerian Herald Friday May 10, 1978, No. 1415,
17. System. ABU Zaria, 1987 p. 135
18. Under dwindling resources. NUC Resource Management in the University
19. Universities; Alternative sources of funding" Resource management in the
20. University System International Seminars NUC/CVC/BC, ABU, Zaria. 1987
21. Balancing Core Values. Retrieved from <http://www.elc-pa.org>, 20/11/12.
22. Core Values. Retrieved from <http://www.ed.fullerton.edu>, 20/11/12.
23. Core Values. Retrieved from Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, 21/11/12.
24. Educational Core Values. Retrieved from <http://www.aesapreacademy.org>, 20/11/12.
25. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). (4th ed). National Policy on Education. Abuja.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).